

Response Equivalence Theory: An Assembly Homogenization Method Integrated with the Response Matrix Method

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ABSTRACT

To account for the boundary condition effect on assembly homogenization, we propose a novel assembly homogenization method called Response Equivalence Theory (RET). RET similarly generates the few-group homogenized constants from a single assembly under reflective boundary conditions. Distinct from existing equivalence theories, RET draws upon the principles of the transport Response Matrix Method (RMM). It introduces Response Correction Factors (RCFs) to ensure that the response relationship before and after homogenization remains consistent. Furthermore, the downstream core diffusion solver for RET is the Response Matrix Method (RMM), rather than the traditional nodal method. To verify the effectiveness of RET, two simplified 2D core problems were constructed, and the calculation results were compared to standard Generalized Equivalence Theory (GET) and OpenMC reference solutions. The preliminary results demonstrate the effectiveness of RET.

Keywords: Response Equivalence Theory (RET), Generalized Equivalence Theory (GET), Response Matrix, Response Correction Factor (RCF), Assembly Homogenization

1. INTRODUCTION

Core physics calculations are essential for reactor analysis and fuel management design. To balance accuracy and computational efficiency, the current mainstream workflow adopts a two-step method: the assembly-level transport calculation generates homogenized few-group constants, while the core-level diffusion calculation uses these constants to compute global reactor parameters [1, 2].

To save computational time, assembly homogenization calculations typically assume reflective boundary conditions on the assembly boundaries. This is acceptable because large Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) cores tend to have a relatively uniform flux distribution and small overall neutron leakage. However, with the emergence of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), designers have gradually realized that the accuracy of the existing “assembly-core” two-step method deteriorates in smaller cores with high neutron leakage [3, 4].

Similar accuracy issues also arise in highly heterogeneous cores, such as the C5G7 benchmark [5, 6], where the spectral interference between UO₂ and MOX assemblies is strong. In such cases, the actual boundary conditions of assemblies deviate significantly from the reflective assumption, making environmental effects non-negligible.

To improve the results of the two-step method, researchers have conducted a series of studies. Koebke proposed “heterogeneity factors” [7], which Smith subsequently generalized as “discontinuity factors” [8]. A key finding of their work is that if the reference solution is available, “equivalence factors” can be used to effectively reproduce the reference solution during the diffusion stage. However, if the reference solution already exists, no correction would be necessary. Furthermore, methods such as

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color-set homogenization [9] and rehomogenization [10] have been developed, which account for core environmental effects to a certain extent.

The Response Matrix Method (RMM) offers an alternative perspective [11, 12, 13]. RMM consists of a cell (local) calculation and a global (core) calculation. The cell stage solves boundary source problems using transport or diffusion theory to pre-calculate assembly response matrices. If the response matrix construction adequately accounts for boundary conditions (environmental effects), transport-based response matrices can achieve transport-level accuracy in the global stage. However, the immense state space defined by burnup, temperature, and boron concentration necessitates repeated transport response calculations, hindering RMM's adoption as a mainstream engineering tool. Nevertheless, the concept of response relation equivalence is highly valuable.

Practically, diffusion response matrices are more accessible [14, 15, 16]. However, their accuracy is inherently limited by diffusion approximations, spatial homogenization, and energy condensation. This paper explores the integration of homogenization with response equivalence concepts, proposing the Response Equivalence Theory (RET). The core objective of RET is to modify the diffusion response matrix of a homogenized assembly to approximate the transport response characteristics of the heterogeneous assembly, thereby preserving response relation conservation.

2. RESPONSE EQUIVALENCE THEORY

RET is built upon the framework of the Response Matrix Method. Due to space limitations, prerequisite knowledge regarding the RMM can be found in reference [12, 13, 16].

Regarding homogenization, RET employs flux-volume weighting to generate few-group constants, similar to existing equivalence theories. This work focuses on ensuring the conservation of response relations. A well-posed problem is defined by conservation equations and definite conditions (initial and boundary conditions). In steady-state neutronics, a unique mapping—or response relation—exists between fixed boundary source conditions and the system solution. Under identical boundary conditions, the response relation of a heterogeneous assembly is described by the transport equation, while that of a homogenized assembly follows the diffusion equation. The discrepancy between these two is termed “response inconsistency.” The following section elucidates this inconsistency from a linear algebra perspective.

Based on the classification of boundary conditions, there are two types of response relations: the response of incoming current to outgoing current, and the response of net current to flux. The second type is used here to illustrate the inconsistency before and after homogenization.

For a heterogeneous assembly, the transport response relationship is:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_t = \mathbf{R}_t \mathbf{I} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the expansion coefficient vector of the boundary net current, \mathbf{R}_t is the transport response matrix, and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_t$ is the expansion coefficient vector of the transport boundary flux.

For the homogenized assembly, under the same boundary conditions, the diffusion response relationship is:

$$\boldsymbol{\varphi}_d = \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{I} \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{R}_d is the diffusion response matrix, and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_d$ is the expansion coefficient vector of the diffusion boundary flux.

Clearly, due to spatial homogenization and diffusion approximation, $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_t$ and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_d$ are not equal under the same boundary net current. This inconsistency is the mathematical manifestation of the difference in response relationships. If the effect of \mathbf{R}_d can be corrected to approximate that of \mathbf{R}_t as closely as possible, the accuracy of downstream core diffusion calculations could potentially be greatly improved.

Homogenization is typically performed under single-assembly reflective boundary conditions. However, in an actual reactor, non-zero net neutron currents exist at all assembly boundaries due to environmental effects. By the principle of superposition, the neutron flux distribution within an assembly can be viewed as a linear superposition of the effects caused by net currents at each boundary. Consequently, modeling the environmental effect at a single boundary suffices, as the method can be generalized to all boundaries.

To model the assembly's behavior under the single-boundary environmental effect, we perform an additional transport calculation on an extended assembly configuration. As shown in Figure 1, by introducing an auxiliary assembly and setting appropriate boundary conditions, a non-zero net current can be induced on a specific boundary of the target assembly. The auxiliary assembly provides an approximate core environmental effect for the target assembly, implying that existing fuel assemblies within the core can be selected as auxiliary assemblies. With a vacuum outer boundary, the auxiliary assembly can be the same as the target assembly. Subsequently, the net current and k_{eff} for the target assembly are extracted. A diffusion fixed boundary source calculation then yields the diffusion flux for the homogenized assembly under the same boundary net current and k_{eff} .

Figure 1. Example of an extended assembly used for modeling single-boundary environment effects.

Evidently, the average diffusion flux and transport flux at the boundary are not equal. Their ratio is defined as the Response Correction Factor (RCF). Taking a 2D, one-group case as an example, the RCF for each boundary k of the target assembly under a non-zero net current is calculated by Eq. (3).

$$f_k = \frac{\bar{\phi}_k^t}{\bar{\phi}_k^d} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\phi}_k^t$ is the average transport flux at boundary k , and $\bar{\phi}_k^d$ is the average diffusion flux at boundary k .

Arranging the RCFs for all boundaries in a specific order gives the vector form of the RCFs for the target assembly under non-zero net current conditions, as shown in Eq. (4).

$$\mathbf{f}^{\text{vec}} = [f_{\text{left}}, f_{\text{up}}, f_{\text{right}}, f_{\text{down}}] \quad (4)$$

The physical meaning of the RCF is to ensure that the integral (or average) of the boundary response flux is as close as possible before and after homogenization under the same net current boundary condition.

Similarly, by placing the elements of Eq. (4) into a diagonal matrix, we obtain the matrix form of the response correction factor, termed the Response Correction Matrix (RCM). If the assembly has rotational symmetry, RCM for non-zero net current on other boundaries can be obtained by rotation. According to the superposition principle, when environmental effects exist on all four sides of the assembly, the

corrected flux takes the form of Eq. (5):

$$\varphi_{md} = \left(\mathbf{M}_d^{\text{left}} \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{C}^{\text{left}} + \mathbf{M}_d^{\text{up}} \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{C}^{\text{up}} + \mathbf{M}_d^{\text{right}} \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{C}^{\text{right}} + \mathbf{M}_d^{\text{down}} \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{C}^{\text{down}} \right) \mathbf{I} \quad (5)$$

where φ_{md} is the corrected boundary diffusion flux expansion coefficient vector, \mathbf{M}_d^k represents the RCM when a non-zero net current exists at node boundary index k , and \mathbf{C}^k is a masking matrix that extracts the net current expansion coefficients for boundary k while setting others to zero (thus its elements are only 1 and 0).

Introducing the corrected diffusion response matrix \mathbf{R}_{md} , Eq. (5) can be rewritten as:

$$\varphi_{md} = \mathbf{R}_{md} \mathbf{I} \quad (6)$$

where the expression for \mathbf{R}_{md} is given in Eq. (7):

$$\mathbf{R}_{md} = \sum_k (\mathbf{M}_d^k \mathbf{R}_d \mathbf{C}^k) \quad (7)$$

The downstream core diffusion calculation method used in conjunction with RET is the Response Matrix Method (RMM), as RMM is well-suited to this decomposition-and-superposition correction concept. In the full-core diffusion calculation, Eq. (7) is used to replace the diffusion response matrix of the homogenized node. How RMM is used for full-core physics calculations can be found in other papers [11, 13, 16]. It is noteworthy that if the diagonal elements of the RCM were replaced by the Discontinuity Factors (DFs), the RMM diffusion calculation would yield the same result as GET. It is important to mention that the Nodal Method, typically paired with DFs, struggles to utilize the RCM. This is because the boundary correction in the Nodal Method is applied as the product of the total neutron flux and the DFs. Therefore, to facilitate comparison, we selected the RMM for the diffusion calculations.

The procedure for calculating the RCFs using RET is summarized as follows:

1. Perform a single-assembly calculation under reflective boundary conditions for the target assembly to obtain few-group homogenized constants.
2. Perform an extended assembly transport calculation on the target assembly to extract the boundary net current, transport flux, and k_{eff} for the target assembly, and then perform group condensation on current and flux.
3. Using the few-group constants from step 1, perform a diffusion fixed boundary source calculation on the homogenized target assembly using the net current and k_{eff} from step 2, and extract the boundary diffusion flux solution.
4. Calculate the RCFs using Eq. (3)

RET utilizes the principle of superposition to decompose the environmental effects of an assembly in the core into the superposition of environmental effects from four boundaries. It generates response factors through additional extended assembly calculations to correct the inconsistent response relations before and after homogenization. In the downstream core diffusion calculation, we use Eq. (6) instead of Eq. (2) for the iterative solution.

3. NUMERICAL TESTS AND RESULTS

To verify the effectiveness of RET, we constructed two 2D core cases: a small PWR with a single enrichment and a small reactor containing MOX fuel assemblies. OpenMC [17] calculation results served as the reference solution. We also compared the results with standard GET. This is because standard GET remains the engineering standard for Light Water Reactor (LWR) physics calculations. As Smith noted in his paper [2], with appropriate diffusion coefficients, reflector parameters, and discontinuity factors,

single-assembly lattice physics calculations with reflective boundaries are sufficient to achieve good results in the downstream diffusion stage. The standard GET parameters were calculated using OpenMC following the methods in reference [2], with reflector parameters obtained via a 1D reflector model. The RET parameters were also calculated using OpenMC. Both GET and RET core physics calculations utilized the RMM, with identical mesh parameters and expansion orders. A detailed comparison of computational cost is beyond the scope of this work. However, since RMM is a coarse-mesh method, its computational burden is generally comparable to nodal methods, with the primary additional cost coming from the extended assembly calculations.

3.1. Small PWR

To initially verify the method's effectiveness, we first selected a small PWR with only one enrichment. The fuel assembly has an enrichment of 3.1%, a length of 21.42 cm, a 17×17 cell lattice, and 25 guide tubes. Its quarter-core layout is shown in Figure 2, with a water reflector and vacuum boundary conditions on the exterior, at normal temperature and pressure. The small overall core size leads to significant neutron leakage, causing the actual boundary conditions between assemblies to deviate notably from the all-reflective assumption.

Figure 2. Small PWR quarter-core layout.

The calculated results for the quarter-core are shown in Figure 3 and Table I. The OpenMC reference solution used 200 million particles, 50 inactive batches, and 500 total batches, reference $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.30862 \pm 0.00003$.

Table I. Comparison of calculation results between RET and GET for the Small PWR.

Method	RET	GET
Error in k_{eff} [pcm]	5	106
Maximum error in assembly power	-0.10%	-0.84%
Average error in assembly power	0.03%	0.40%

1.5785	0.9345	
0.03%	0.00%	
0.46%	-0.14%	
0.9345	0.5526	reference
0.00%	-0.10%	error of RET
-0.14%	-0.84%	error of GET

Figure 3. Small PWR assembly power distribution using RET and GET.

From the results in Table I, the RET k_{eff} error is much smaller than that of GET. Similarly, RET outperforms GET in both maximum and average assembly power deviations. These results preliminarily demonstrate the effectiveness of RET. This also suggests the possibility that, with appropriate RCFs, the transport solution can be reproduced very accurately at the assembly scale.

3.2. MOX Assembly Core

The C5G7 benchmark problem is a 7-group test core with material homogenization [5]. To test the effectiveness of the new equivalence method at the assembly scale, we constructed a C5G7-like test problem, whose UO₂ and MOX fuel assembly materials and geometry are taken from the benchmark [18]. Both fuel assemblies have a width of 21.42 cm. With the exception of the fuel pin cells, the rest are guide tube cells. We used OpenMC to calculate the two-group homogenized parameters for the assemblies. The quarter-core layout of the C5G7-like test problem is consistent with the C5G7 benchmark, as shown in Figure 4, with a water reflector and vacuum boundary conditions on the exterior. The core is small and highly non-uniform, which results in large net neutron currents at the interfaces between fuel assemblies. The assemblies clearly deviate from the reflective boundary condition, which indicates strong environment effects.

Figure 4. C5G7-like core quarter-core layout.

The calculated results for the quarter-core are shown in Table II and Figure 5. The OpenMC reference solution used 200 million particles, 50 inactive batches, and 500 total batches, with reference $k_{\text{eff}} =$

1.17085 ± 0.00003.

Table II. Comparison of calculation results between RET and GET for the C5G7-like core.

Method	RET	GET
Error in k_{eff} [pcm]	-187	528
Maximum error in assembly power	-0.85%	2.33%
Average error in assembly power	0.48%	1.88%

1.7122	0.8910	
-0.17%	0.41%	
2.33%	-1.78%	
0.8910	0.5058	reference
0.41%	-0.85%	error of RET
-1.78%	-1.62%	error of GET

Figure 5. C5G7-like core assembly power distribution using RET and GET.

Compared with GET, the k_{eff} error of RET is reduced by 65%. The average assembly power error for RET is 0.48%, and the maximum assembly power error is less than 1%. These calculation results demonstrate that RET offers a significant advantage in overcoming the environment effect.

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a novel equivalence homogenization method within the framework of the Response Matrix Method, termed Response Equivalence Theory (RET). RET integrates the concepts of homogenization and response equivalence, employing Response Correction Factors to ensure that the response relations before and after homogenization remain as consistent as possible. The RCF is calculated through an additional extended assembly calculation. Although this increases the computational cost of the upstream assembly calculation, the resulting improvement in accuracy is significant. Numerical results from two test cases preliminarily demonstrate the effectiveness of RET. In future work, we intend to test more complex and realistic core problems and conduct a more comprehensive comparison with Generalized Equivalence Theory (GET).

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